

**THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN HAS BECOME SALTY AND HAS BEEN SUBJECTED TO
SOCIALIZATION PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF LAND RECLAMATION**

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the reclamation measures of the salinized and various degrees of salinization of soils in the Agdash region with the application of organic-mineral meliorates. In the conducted chemical melioration method, the effect of chemical improvements prepared based on wood and cane sawdust on the improvement of the saline-salinized soils of the Agdash region was studied. During the washing experiment, chemical meliorates were 10 tons per hectare, and the washing rate was 8 thousand m³/ha. The obtained results were compared with the results of the experiments carried out with ordinary water and with delay, and it was determined that the data obtained from the washing variants with the application of chemical meliorates were almost twice higher than the results of the control variants. In the washing experiment carried out with the application of chemical improvements, soil fertility was eliminated. The alkalinity of the soil solution decreased from 8.1 to 7.0-7.1, and the residual amount of water-insoluble gypsum remaining in the soil increased more than 2 times compared to the option of washing with ordinary water, which indicates that the water-physical properties of the reclamation soils have a direct positive effect on improving soil fertility.

Keywords: Melioration, washing, meliorate, salinization, ostracization, granulomere composition.

Introduction. The total land fund of the Republic of Azerbaijan is 8641.5 thousand hectares. 4514.4 thousand hectares of this area are suitable for the cultivation of agricultural plants [1-3]. If we take into account that approximately 30% of these areas have been subjected to various salinization and salinization, it is not difficult to understand how important and important work is the development of currently developed chemical meliorates and new washing technologies with their application and their implementation in production conditions on the territory of the republic. For this purpose, the research conducted by us and the results obtained from them are of great importance for the development of the republic's agriculture [4-6]. This issue significantly boosts the fulfillment of the food security of the population of the republic, which was set before us by Mr. Ilham Aliyev, the head of state [7-8]. If we consider that every 0.1% reduction in soil salinity leads to an increase in productivity of about one quintal per hectare, then it becomes clear how relevant the research is today.

Purpose of work. It is the development of the technology for the preparation of chemical meliorants, which ensures the reduction of irrigation water and washing time, and their application in production conditions for the improvement of salinized and mainly salinized soils in the territory of the Republic.

The object of the study. The area is the saline-saline lands of the Agdash district, which is located in the Aran economic-geographical region of the republic.

To achieve the goal, the following issues have been put forward:

- Selection of waste suitable for this purpose in the territory of the republic for preparation of chemical meliorates, investigation of their chemical, mechanical, water-physical, and agronomic properties;

- Development of the technology of preparation of chemical ameliorants based on selected wastes;

Research methodology. The scientific research conducted at present and the well-known methods widely used in the territory of the republic were tested [9-10].

X-ray spectral and X-ray diffractometric analyses and mineralogical controls of the raw materials and materials used during the research were carried out in the "Centers for the collective use of academic devices and Equipment" of the "Geology and Geophysics" Institute of ANAS on "58 Tiger", "Muniflex 600 and ICP MS 7700" devices.

The composition of the soil and filtered filtrate. The water weight analysis of the soil sample was carried out in the "Laboratory of Mass Soil Analysis" of "Baku Abadlig Service MMC" based on the following methods:

- Amount of alkalinity produced by normal cations - DÖST-31869-2012; Chlorine anion determination - DÖST-26425-85; sulfate ion determination - DÖST-26426-85; calcium cation quantity determination - DÖST-26428-85; determination of the amount of magnesium cation - DÖST-26428-85;

- When determining the amount of bases absorbed in the soil;

- Amount of absorbed calcium- DÖST-26487-85; the amount of absorbed magnesium - DÖST-26487-85;

determination of absorbed sodium was carried out according to DÖST-26950-86.

In addition, calcium carbonate DÖST-26424-85 in soil samples; determination of water-insoluble gypsum was carried out according to DÖST-26487-85;

The amount of humus in the soil was determined according to DÖST-26213-91, and the amount of ph with MW 101 PRO brand ph meter according to DÖST 8.857-2013.

The agricultural tests of the prepared chemical ameliorants were carried out under laboratory conditions in special containers with a height of 55 cm, a diameter of 5 cm, and a mesh bottom in the following order:

The air-dried soil sample, with a pre-determined degree of salinity and salinity, is crushed and passed through a sieve. A specified amount of soil sample is mixed with a chemical ameliorant and filled in special containers to have a density of 1.4 g/cm³ and lightly beaten until the density is 1.4 g/cm³ (until the required level is obtained in the container). A calculated amount of washing water is given to the soil from the top of the pots. After the 5,000 m³/ha washing rate is given for each account, the seepage rate is measured and filtered water samples are taken for chemical analysis. 3-4 days after the full washing rate is given, the soil is emptied

from the washing containers, dried in the weather for 5-10 days, and subjected to chemical analysis.

DISSERTATION

During the experiment, the rate of ameliorant was 10 t/ha, and the rate of washing was 8 thousand m³/ha in all options. The experiment was carried out in the following options:

1. Wash-control with ordinary water;
2. Wash control by delaying;
3. Washing with sawdust soaked in 20% H₂SO₄;
4. Wash with cane sawdust soaked in 20% H₂SO₄;

Modern land reclamation condition of Agdash region. The Aran economic-geographical region, where Agdash district is located, covers the Kura-Araz plain along the lower course of the Kura-Araz rivers. According to the maintenance of the region, it is divided into five large parts - Shirvan, Karabakh, Mil, Mugan, and Salyan - by the Kura and Araz rivers. On the Shirvan plain, the Agdash region's climatic conditions significantly impact other regions bordering it. The average annual air temperature in the region is 14.2°C, precipitation is 503 mm, average air humidity is 71%, evaporation from the soil is 930 mm, and the average annual temperature of the soil is 17°C. Climate indicators of the region are given in Table 1 of the Agdash metrological station.

Table 1.

Main climate indicators of the Agdash

	Climate indicators	By chapters				Average annual	Seasons of the year	
		Winter	Summer	winter	autumn		Hot	Cold
1	Air temperature	3,2	12,9	25,3	15,2	14,2	19,1	9,2
2	Precipitation	109	157	91	144	503	233	270
3	Relative humidity of the air	81	71	57	75	71	63	79
4	Evaporation	81	202	453	194	930	712	218
5	Soil surface temperature	3,3	16,0	31,7	17,3	17,0	26,1	7,5

The total irrigated area of the Agdash region is 34521 hectares. 13,116 hectares of it are unsalinated and 21,405 hectares are saline lands [12]. Complete

information on the salinization of irrigated areas is given in the table below.

Table 2

Salinity and drainage condition of irrigated lands of Agdash region,, hectare. %

c/c	Common area	The degree of salinity in the 0-1 m layer					Drained areas	
		unsalted	salted	including			total	of that sentence closed horizontal
				weak	medium	severe		
1	<u>34521</u> 20,0	<u>13116</u> 38,0	<u>21405</u> 62,0	<u>10880</u> 50,8	<u>8108</u> 37,9	<u>2417</u> 11,3	<u>19940</u> 57,8	<u>19940</u> 57,8

As can be seen from the data, 10,880 hectares of the irrigated lands of the Agdash region are poorly, 8,108 hectares and 2,417 hectares are severely saline (table 2).

The degree of ownership of lands located in the region is different. Almost all of the total irrigated lands

have been subjected to various degrees of scarification [17]. 32,485 hectares of deforested areas and 94.1% of the total area are weak, and 2,036 hectares or 5.9% are moderately and severely deforested lands (table 3).

Table 3.

Fertility status of irrigated lands of Agdash region, hectare %

c/c	Common area	Without support	Salinity level in 1 m layer		
			Cheerful total	including	
				weak	medium
1	<u>34521</u> 100	-	<u>34521</u> 100	<u>32485</u> 94,1	<u>2036</u> 5,9

When examining the information about the land reclamation condition of the Agdash region, it is known that the lands of the area are in a very poor state of land reclamation and there is a great need for environmental improvement of these areas.

The initial amount of calcium carbonate in the soil decreased to 7.10 and 7.11% by 0.07% in the upper layer and 0.09% in the lower layer during washing with ordinary water. In the delayed washing option, these values were 6.89 and 7.01% for layers, respectively, and 7.10% in the bottom ash option.

Result

During the conducted scientific research, the following conclusions were reached:

1. The soils of the Agdash region have been exposed to various degrees of salinization and salinization.

2. During the cultivation of these lands, to obtain a normal amount of productivity, melioration measures should be carried out, especially chemical melioration works, before appropriation.

3. Comparative efficiency of chemical meliorates late and bottom ash During the research it was determined that late is more efficient than bottom ash. The possibility of reducing the degree of salinization of the upper layer of the soil to 0.796% and the degree of salinity of the lower 25-50 cm layer to 1.061% during washing with 8 thousand m³/ha of water rate by adding 10 tons per hectare was determined as a result of the research. the lower layer.

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